

“A Descriptive Study To Assess The Stressors, The Level Of Stress And Coping Mechanism Among Post-Basic B.Sc. Nursing Students At Selected Nursing Colleges In Jabalpur”

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ABSTRACT: This descriptive study aimed to assess stressors, stress levels, and coping mechanisms among Post-Basic B.Sc. Nursing students in selected nursing colleges in Jabalpur. A quantitative research design was employed, with 100 students selected using purposive sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed that 28% of students experienced mild stress, 71% moderate stress, and 1% severe stress. Stressors were classified as mild (25%), moderate (48%), and severe (27%). Coping mechanisms varied, with 24% demonstrating poor coping, 68% moderate coping, and 8% good coping. Significant correlations were identified between stressors and coping strategies, particularly with emotional, social, and diversional supports. The results highlight the prevalence of moderate stress levels among nursing students and the importance of enhancing coping mechanisms to manage stress effectively. Interventions tailored to specific stress domains, such as emotional and cognitive stress, are recommended to promote well-being and resilience in nursing education.

KEYWORDS: *Nursing students, Stressors, Coping Mechanisms, Perceived Stress, Demographic variables, Stress Management, Well-being*

INTRODUCTION

Stress can be defined as a state of worry or mental tension caused by a difficult situation. Stress is a natural human response that prompts us to address challenges and threats in our lives. Everyone experiences stress to some degree. The way we respond to stress, however, makes a big difference to our overall well-being.

WHO, 2023

Stress is experienced when a body responds to any kind of excessive demand; stress can be caused by both good and bad experiences. When a body feels stressed by something around, it reacts by releasing chemicals into the blood, which gives the body more energy and strength. This can be a good thing, if the stress is caused by physical activity. Similarly, it can be a bad thing when stress is in response to an emotional instance and there is no outlet for this extra energy and strength. In this blog we will be discussing about – the different causes of stress, how it affects you, the difference between ‘good’ or ‘positive’ stress and ‘bad’ or ‘negative’ stress, and some common facts about how stress affects people today.

Positive stress

Positive stress can inspire people to do their best and perform better than if they were under no pressure. Positive stress has the following characteristics:

- Motivates, focuses energy
- Positive stress is a coping ability
- Provides excitement

- Improves performance – both physical and psychological

Negative stress

Negative stress is the opposite of Positive stress. The characteristics are as follows:

- Negative stress causes anxiety
- Feels unpleasant
- Decreases endurance and/or performance
- May lead to both physical and psychological problems

MANIPAL HOSPITALS, 2019

Stress is defined as "a particular relationship between the person and the environment that is appraised by the person as taxing or exceeding his or her resources and endangering his or her well-being"

KINGDON & HALVORSEN, 2006

Stress is a common human experience blamed for many ills. Stressors can be broadly defined as situations or events that potentially affect health outcomes because there is a gap between students' needs in a specific clinical case and their resources or ability to cope with a task or situation. Stress, according to Selye, is a response to environmental stimuli. In the physical environment, stress results when 1 body exerts demands on another, such as 1 object placed on top of another thing: if the second object cannot withstand the pressure from the first object, the stress or anxiety it is exerting can cause the second object to collapse. Similarly, in biological systems such as the human body, unmitigated or uncontrolled stress can lead to physical and mental collapse, which ultimately can result in adverse health outcomes.

NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF STRESS, 2022

A certain level of stress is considered to be a positive motivator to reach a goal, but too much stress can adversely affect physical and mental health

CHIAUZZI, BREVARD, 2008

Stress can lead to negative physical and emotional consequences such as irritability, fatigue, anxiety, and lack of energy or motivation. Stress can be brief, situational, and a positive force motivating performance, but if experienced over an extended period of time it can become chronic stress, which negatively impacts health and well-being.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

"A Descriptive Study To Assess The Stressors, The Level Of Stress And Coping Mechanism Among Post-Basic B.Sc. Nursing Students At Selected Nursing Colleges In Jabalpur"

AIM

Our main aim is to evaluate the level of stress among Post Basic B.Sc. nursing students systematically.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1. Assess the stressor among Post Basic B.Sc. nursing students in selected nursing colleges in Jabalpur.
2. Assess the level of stress among Post Basic B.Sc. nursing students in selected nursing colleges in Jabalpur.
3. Assess the coping mechanism among Post Basic B.Sc. nursing students in selected nursing colleges in Jabalpur.
4. Find out the relationship between sub-factors of stress and coping mechanisms among Post Basic B.Sc. nursing students in selected nursing colleges in Jabalpur.
5. Find out the significant association between stress and coping strategies among Post Basic B.Sc. nursing students with their selected demographic variables.

HYPOTHESES

1. **H1:** There will be a significant stressor among Post Basic B.Sc. nursing students in selected nursing in Jabalpur.
2. **H2:** There will be a significant level of stress among Post Basic B.Sc. nursing students in selected nursing colleges in Jabalpur.
3. **H3:** There will be a significant coping mechanism among Post Basic B.Sc. nursing students in selected nursing colleges in Jabalpur.
4. **H4:** There will be a significant correlation between sub-factors of stress and coping mechanisms.
5. **H5:** There will be a significant association between the level of stress and coping strategies among Post Basic B.Sc. nursing students in selected nursing colleges in Jabalpur with their selected demographic variables.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: A quantitative research approach and non-experimental descriptive research design was adopted for the study. The sample for the study was 100 Post-Basic B.Sc. nursing students chosen by purposive sampling technique from Jabalpur Institute of Nursing, and Government Nursing College NSCB in Jabalpur. A structured questionnaire consisting of demographic variables, stressor assessment, and coping scales was used to collect data. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including mean, median, standard deviation, correlation analysis, and chi-square tests. A small preliminary investigation of the same general character was conducted at the Yogmani Institute of Nursing where 10 samples were chosen by purposive sampling technique by the tool-modified PSS scale for stress, stressor, and coping. The result of (section I - $r = 0.75$, section II - $r = 0.76$, section III - $r = 0.93$)

RESULTS: The findings revealed that the majority of nursing students faced 28% reported mild stress, 71% reported moderate stressors, with moderate levels of perceived stress and 1% reported severe stress. The cumulative percentage indicates that 99% of respondents reported experiencing at least a moderate level of stress. The distribution of respondents based on the level of stressor Out of the 100 respondents, 25% reported mild stressors, 48% reported moderate stressors, and 27% reported severe stressors. The cumulative percentages indicate that 73% of the respondents experienced at least a moderate level of stress. the level of coping among the respondents. The data reveals that 24% of the respondents reported poor coping, 68% reported moderate coping, and 8% reported good coping. The cumulative percentages indicate that 92% of the respondents reported at least a moderate level of coping. Most students reported having moderate coping skills, while some struggled with effective coping. Various coping strategies were employed, including positive thinking, spiritual support, social support, emotional support, and diversional activity. Significant correlations were found between certain stressors and coping mechanisms, indicating the influence of stressors on the choice of coping strategies.

Level Of Coping

Level Of Coping	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Poor Coping	24	24%	24%	27%
Moderate Coping	68	68%	68%	92%
Good Coping	8	8%	8%	100%
Total	100	100%	100%	

Table 1: provides insights into the level of coping among the respondents. The data reveals that 24% of the respondents reported poor coping, 68% reported moderate coping, and 8% reported good coping. The cumulative percentages indicate that 92% of the respondents reported at least a moderate level of coping.

DISCUSSION: The results highlight the importance of understanding and addressing the stressors experienced by nursing students. The findings suggest the need for targeted interventions and support systems to enhance stress management skills and promote overall well-being among nursing students. The correlations between stressors and coping mechanisms provide insights into the coping strategies that may be effective in specific stressor domains. The Correlations between sub-factors of stress and coping mechanisms in the case of physical stress ($r = 1.000$, $p < 0.001$), spiritual support ($r = 0.234$, $p = 0.019$), and diversional activity ($r = 0.211$, $p = 0.035$), Emotional stress exhibits a strong positive correlation with emotional support ($r = 0.959$, $p < 0.001$), diversional activity ($r = 0.553$, $p < 0.001$), social support ($r = 0.444$, $p < 0.001$). Social stress shows a strong positive correlation with social support ($r = 0.812$, $p < 0.001$), spiritual support ($r = 0.370$, $p < 0.001$), diversional activity ($r = 0.227$, $p = 0.023$), and emotional support ($r = 0.217$, $p = 0.030$), Cognitive stress displays significant positive correlations with positive thinking ($r = 0.276$, $p = 0.005$), emotional support ($r = 0.345$, $p < 0.001$), social support ($r = 0.271$, $p = 0.006$), spiritual support ($r = 0.579$, $p < 0.001$), and diversional activity ($r = 0.516$, $p < 0.001$), spiritual stress exhibits strong positive correlations with emotional support ($r = 0.522$, $p < 0.001$), social support ($r = 0.294$, $p = 0.003$), and diversional activity ($r = 0.880$, $p < 0.001$), significantly correlated at 0.05 level of significance. And the Association on level of stress with the selected demographic variable of Nursing students There was no significant association observed in any of the demographic.

CONCLUSION: This study concludes that nursing students experience moderate levels of stress and employ various coping mechanisms to manage stress. The findings underscore the importance of considering individual stressors and tailoring coping strategies to address specific stress domains. The study highlights the significance of providing support and resources to enhance the well-being of nursing students and suggests directions for future research in stress

management and coping interventions in nursing education.

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